

THE SULPHONATION OF MONOETHYLANILINE

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The sulphonation of monoethylaniline and the *N*-ethylation of *p*-toluene-sulphonyl-sulphanilic, metanilic and orthanilic acids, has been studied and it has been found that the sulphonation proceeds exactly as in the case of monomethylaniline.

While preparing certain wetting agents by condensing oleic acid with *N*-methylsulphanilic acid (Dhingra, Uppal and Venkataraman, *J. Soc. Dyers & Col.*, 1936, **52**, 91), the constitution of the latter as the *para* compound was assumed. In view of the somewhat conflicting nature of the existing evidence regarding the three monomethylaniline sulphonic acids, proof of their orientation was later adduced (Uppal and Venkataraman, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1938, **57**, 410). Sulphonation of monomethylaniline leads according to the conditions of sulphonation, to *N*-methylsulphanilic acid or a mixture of this acid and *N*-methyl-metanilic acid. *N*-methyl-orthanilic acid has been obtained by the methylation of orthanilic acid with dimethyl sulphate. The three monomethylaniline sulphonic acids are characterised as the arylamine salts of their *p*-toluenesulphonyl derivatives, the latter being prepared both by treating the monomethylaniline sulphonic acids with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and by the *N*-methylation of *p*-toluenesulphonyl-sulphanilic, metanilic and orthanilic acids. Halberkann (*Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 1836) established the position of the sulphonic group in *N*-methylsulphanilic acid by preparing its *p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative and comparing it with the product of the methylation of *N*-*p*-toluenesulphonylsulphanilic acid.

Studying the sulphonation of monoethylaniline and the *N*-ethylation of *p*-toluenesulphonyl-sulphanilic, metanilic and orthanilic acids on parallel lines, it has been found that the sulphonation proceeds exactly as in the case of monomethylaniline.

The preparation of *N*-ethylsulphanilic acid (I) was described in G.P.

(I)

(II)

295, 104 (1916); monoethylaniline was slowly added in the cold to sulphuric acid monohydrate, followed by the gradual addition of 80% fuming

sulphuric acid, the whole mixture being heated at 150-70° for about 2-3 hours, till there was no trace of free base. The m.p. of the substance was not quoted.

In *G.P.* 48, 151 (1889) the preparation of *N*-ethyl-metanilic acid (II) has been claimed by direct ethylation of metanilic acid. Gnehm and Scheutz (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1901, ii, 63, 414) prepared the same acid (II) (decomposing at 294°). These authors sulphonated ethylaniline by adding it to double the required amount of 25% fuming sulphuric acid and then adding 3 times the weight of 75% fuming acid, the temperature being kept below 50°. After dilution and working up in the manner described, (II) was obtained in needles, the substance (I) accompanying it in small amounts.

No attempts have been recorded in the literature regarding the preparation of *N*-ethyl-orthanilic acid (III).

The sulphonation of monoethylaniline with 20% fuming sulphuric acid at 185-90° leads to a single product, decomposing at 259°, identified as the *p*-acid (I). When the base is sulphonated at 50°, using 80% fuming sulphuric acid in the later stages of the reaction, the product is a mixture of the *m*-acid (II) (decomp. 286°) and the *p*-acid (I) (decomp. 259°) (*cf.* Gnehm and Scheutz, *loc. cit.*). Keeping the temperature at or below 50°, the proportion of the two acids appeared to depend on the strength of the sulphuric acid. Under our conditions the formation of the *p*-acid is about twice as much as that of the *m*-acid, although the actual quantity of the pure *p*-acid isolated is smaller on account of the repeated crystallisation necessary for complete purification. The course of the reactions under the various conditions described is, therefore, precisely parallel to the course of the reactions in the case of monomethylaniline (*loc. cit.*):

On ethylating orthanilic acid with diethylsulphate (*cf.* Houben and Schreiber, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2346) the *o*-acid (III) is obtained (decomp. 212-13°). As in the case of the monomethylaniline sulphonic acids, the three isomers have been oriented by an application of Halberkann's method (*loc. cit.*). Each of the three aniline sulphonic acids is converted into its *N*-*p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative (*e.g.* IV) which is ethylated with

(IV)

diethylsulphate and sodium hydroxide to yield the corresponding *N*-ethyl derivative (V).

The three *N*-ethylaniline-sulphonic acids have been condensed with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and the products compared with those referred to above. As the free acids are not readily isolable the actual comparison made is of the arylamine salts (Forster and Keyworth, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 165T), the *p*-chloroaniline salt being convenient to use.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

N-Ethylsulphanilic Acid (I).—To fuming sulphuric acid (20%, 150 g.) contained in a 200 c.c. wide-mouthed round-bottomed flask fitted with an air condenser and a calcium chloride tube, monoethylaniline (50 g.) was slowly added through the condenser and the mixture heated in an oil-bath at 190° for 4 hours. The dark coloured mixture, after cooling, was gently poured into ice-cold acetone (2 litres) with occasional stirring and kept in the refrigerator overnight. The dark solid mass (65 g.) was collected at the pump and washed with more of acetone, till the filtrate was practically colourless.

The crude product was recrystallised (Norit) from the minimum amount of water (about 200 c.c.), filtered at the pump, washed with water till free from sulphuric acid and dried at 110°, m.p. 259° (decomp.). The final yield was 22 g. Much of the acid dissolved in cold water during the removal of sulphuric acid. The pure product after further recrystallisation from thrice the amount of water had unchanged m.p.

N-Ethyl-metanilic Acid (II).—The method followed was the same as in the case of *N*-methyl-metanilic acid (*loc. cit.*). Monoethylaniline (50 g.) was added slowly to ice-cold and mechanically agitated fuming sulphuric acid (20%, 100 g.) at such a rate that the temperature of the reaction mixture did not rise above 50°. When the whole of the ethylaniline had been added, the temperature was raised to 60° which was maintained for 15 minutes. The flask was again externally cooled and fuming sulphuric acid (80%, 150 g.) was run in, keeping the temperature

below 40°. The mixture was kept at this temperature for about 30 minutes (till it gave a clear solution in alkaline water) and then poured with stirring into ice-cold acetone (2 litres) and kept overnight in the refrigerator. The yellow solid (66 g.) was filtered at the pump, washed with acetone and dried at 110°. The crude product was recrystallised from water (Norit), collected on the pump, and washed with ice-cold water till free from sulphuric acid, colourless crystals, m.p. 252°, (decomp.) yield 36 g. After recrystallisation from 120 c.c. of water at room temperature, 16 g. of crystals (decomp. at 286°) were obtained, and on further recrystallisation the m.p. remained unchanged.

On concentrating all the mother-liquors and recrystallising the solid obtained therefrom, 30 g. of the product free from sulphuric acid and decomposing at 247° were obtained; this product on repeated fractional crystallisation giving 8 g. more of the ethyl-metanilic acid (decomp. 286°). From the mother-liquor 15 g. of ethylsulphanilic acid were recovered. Its identity with the *p*-acid obtained in the previous experiment was proved by conversion into the *p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative and its *p*-chloroaniline salt (*vide infra*).

N-Ethyl-orthanilic Acid (III).—Orthanilic acid (5 g.) and sodium carbonate (1.6 g.) were dissolved in warm water (20 c.c.) and the solution shaken with diethylsulphate (8 c.c.). The mixture was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour and the clear red solution concentrated to a small bulk and cooled. The precipitate (2 g.) was collected and washed with alcohol. On recrystallisation from water the product melted at 212-13° (decomp.). (Purity by titration, 99.9%).

p-Chloroaniline Salt (VI) of *p*-Toluenesulphonyl-*N*-ethylsulphanilic Acid (V).—*N*-Ethylsulphanilic acid (5 g., decomp. 259°), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4.8 g.) and pyridine (15 c.c.) were heated together in an oil-bath at 140° for 3 hours. The mixture was then dissolved in water and neutralised with caustic soda solution (33.9 c.c. of 1.8*N*), the pyridine boiled off and the solution reduced to a small bulk. On acidifying with hydrochloric acid and cooling, the product which separated was collected and crystallised from alcohol. It was then converted into the *p*-chloroaniline salt by the addition of *p*-chloroaniline hydrochloride, the precipitated salt filtered at the pump and washed with cold water to remove traces of hydrochloric acid and free *p*-chloroaniline hydrochloride. The m.p. was 217-18° after drying at 110°. (0.1572 G. required 3.2 c.c. of *N*/10-caustic soda. Calc. 3.25 c.c. : purity 98.5%).

Ethylation of p-Toluenesulphonylsulphanilic Acid (IV).—The pyridine salt (6 g.) of *p*-toluenesulphonylsulphanilic acid was neutralised with sodium hydroxide (phenolphthalein), the pyridine boiled off, and the residue cooled and shaken with diethylsulphate (5 c.c.) for about 10 minutes. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath and treated alternately with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and diethylsulphate till ethylation was complete. On cooling and acidifying the reaction mixture with hydrochloric acid no precipitate separated, and the product was isolated as the *p*-chloroaniline salt by adding *p*-chloroaniline hydrochloride. The m.p. of the crystallised product and the mixed m.p. with (VI) was 217°. (0.1894 G. required 3.9 c.c. of *N*/₁₀-caustic soda solution. Calc. 3.92 c.c.; purity 99.5%).

p-Chloroaniline Salt of p-Toluenesulphonyl-N-ethyl-metanilic Acid.—*N*-Ethyl-metanilic acid was condensed with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and the *p*-chloroaniline salt (VII) isolated directly as above. The m.p. was 111°. (0.2412 G. required 5 c.c. of *N*/₁₀-caustic soda. Calc. 5 c.c.; purity 100%).

Ethylation of p-Toluenesulphonyl-metanilic Acid.—The condensation mixture of metanilic acid (5 g.) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (5.5 g.) was neutralised, the pyridine removed as usual and the mixture ethylated with diethylsulphate (25 c.c.) and caustic soda solution (10%, 150 c.c.) as in the ethylation of *p*-toluenesulphonylsulphanilic acid, and finally the product was isolated as the *p*-chloroaniline salt. On adding *p*-chloroaniline hydrochloride, an oily mass settled down, which, on standing for some time in the refrigerator, solidified. 0.1428 G. required 2.95 c.c. of *N*/₁₀-caustic soda solution. Calc. 2.96 c.c.; purity 99.6%. The salt melted at 111° (mixed m.p. with VII was 111°).

p-Chloroaniline[Salt of *p*-Toluenesulphonyl-*N*-ethyl-orthanilic Acid — On condensing *N*-ethyl-orthanilic acid with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride as above, and converting into the *p*-chloroaniline salt, the latter, after recrystallisation, melted at 181–83°.

Ethylation of p-Toluenesulphonyl-orthanilic Acid —The sodium salt of *p*-toluenesulphonyl-orthanilic acid (2 g.) was dissolved in a small amount of water and ethylated with diethylsulphate (15 c.c.) and caustic soda solution (10%, 40 c.c.) heating the mixture on the water-bath for 90 minutes. The mixture was cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid, but no product separated. On adding excess of *p*-chloroaniline hydrochloride

solution, the oily mass, which first separated contained the unethylated substance, as it did not give a sharp end-point when titrated against caustic soda solution. On keeping the mother-liquor overnight in the refrigerator, the *N*-ethyl derivative, giving a sharp end-point, was obtained. 0.1338 G. required 2.8 c.c. of *N*/10-caustic soda solution. Calc. 2.8 c.c. It melted at 183°, undepressed by admixture with the previously prepared substance.

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